

PHARMACOECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF MEDICINES USED IN THE TREATMENT OF PNEUMONIA AND THEIR PRICING MECHANISMS

Kulmamatova B.K.

Suyunov N.D.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

Osh State University, Faculty of Medicine, Osh, Kyrgyz Republic

e-mail: bacun.kulmamatova@gmail.com

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Relevance: community-acquired pneumonia (VP) retains a leading position in the structure of infectious morbidity, with an annual incidence of 5-20 cases per 1,000 population. The problem is of particular medical and social importance in risk groups: children under 5 years of age (15-20% of all cases), people over 65 years of age (30-40% of hospitalizations), and immunocompromised patients.

Purpose of the study: to study the prices of medicines used in the treatment of pneumonia.

Materials and methods: statistical data from the official source, Dary-Darmek, developed by the Department of Medicines and Medical Devices of the Kyrgyz Republic, was used as the information base of the study. Comparative statistical analysis was used to process the data, which made it possible to assess the dynamics and structure of sales. The results of the analysis were interpreted using logical analysis to formulate scientific conclusions and practical recommendations.

Results: let's consider the pricing of medicines used in the treatment of the disease, pneumonia. The pharmacotherapeutic group beta-lactam antibacterial drugs of the active substance or the international name Ampicillin is present in the Dary-Darmek mobile application developed by the Department of Medicines and Medical Devices of the Kyrgyz Republic, including maximum and minimum prices with different trade names, as well as the same international nonproprietary names, doses, and forms that differ in trade names. as follows. The medicinal product of the trade name Ampicillin sodium salt, for injection, 0.5 g, 1 g, No. 50, manufacturer OAO Sintez, Russia, supplier OOO Neman, is sold at a retail price of 43-65 soms. The medicinal product of the trade name Ampicillin sodium salt, for injection, 0.5 g, 1 g, No. 50, manufacturer OAO Sintez, Russia, supplier OOO Apteka kg, is sold at a retail price of 28.06-59.65 soms. The average price of 3 chain pharmacies by one manufacturer is 34.35 som.

The medicinal product of the trade name "AMOCLAVIN-AMT", tablets, 1,000 mg No. 10, manufactured by Deva Holding, Turkey, Turkey, supplier of the Neman LLC pharmacy chain, is sold at a retail price of 653 som. The medicinal product of the trade name "Amoxiclav", tablets, 1000mg No. 10, manufacturer "Lek D.D., Slovenia", Slovenia, network pharmacy LLC "Era pharm", is sold at a retail price of 611.09 som. The average price of 3 chain pharmacies of two manufacturers is 659.03 soms. The medicinal product of the trade name "CEF 3", for injection, 1g, No. 1, manufacturer Himpharm, Kazakhstan, Kazakhstan, supplier of the online pharmacy LLC Neman, is sold at a retail price of 255 som. The medicinal product of the trade name "Ceftas", for injection, 1g, No. 1, produced by Cooper Pharma Limited, India, pharmacy chain LLC "Apteka kg", is sold at a retail price of 276.2 som, the average price of 3 chain pharmacies of two manufacturers is 265.2 som.

Conclusions: the treatment of pneumonia requires an integrated approach, including the use of various groups of drugs depending on the type of pathogen and the severity of the patient's condition. Drug pricing is associated with many factors that can significantly affect the availability of therapy. It is important to pay attention to the effectiveness of treatment and ensure access to the necessary drugs to reduce the incidence and mortality from pneumonia.